

Role of ICT in Empowering Women in Self Help Groups in Chennai City

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Abstract

Women form a significant source of human resource in a developing country like India. Women's development has ripple effect on herself, her family and the society as a whole. Self Help Groups, shortly SHG's are of recent development which aims at developing and empowering women economically and socially. This group provides employment and income which leads to sustainable development of women and also her family. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) are modern means to collect and disseminate information and knowledge for the personal and professional development of an individual particularly women. Women, both in rural and urban areas are well aware of the ICT tools and techniques and utilize its functions for their development. These functions can be used for entertainment, education and professional purposes. The recent developments in ICT such as e-commerce, e-banking, e-marketing, internet etc have been widely used by women in SHGs for developing their economic activities. In this context, this paper intends to study the role and significance of ICT in women SHGs and also identify the challenges faced by women while using ICT tools and devices. The research uses both primary data to study the objectives and secondary data for review of literature and concluded that ICT plays a vital role in the economic, social, educational, technical and political development of women in a country.

Introduction

Women play a vital role in the economic development of a country particularly in a developing country like India. Women are a major source of human resource and development of women has ripple effect. In the early decades, the role of women was confined to domestic chores, looking after her husband and children. In the recent years there has been a drastic change in the role played by women in her family and society. Women now play the role as home makers as well as employed in corporate sectors, entrepreneurs and do work from home for flexibility in time. All these are possible because of the scrupulous efforts of the government both Centre and State, NGOs, social activists and feminists. Their efforts had enhanced the rate of literacy among women and this paved way for employment and self

employment. Education is a significant pre-requisite and a powerful tool for empowerment of women. Education empowers women for to uplift her economic and social status and also the status of her family. In the present scenario, ICT plays a magnificent role in the empowerment of women and various measures have been taken by the government to impart education using ICT tools to girls and women because the delivery of information through these devices are easy and reach the beneficiaries immediately and also creates awareness and opportunities.

ICT and Women's Empowerment

In the global scenario, the Sustainable Development Goals aims at achieving gender equality and developing women by empowering them in the use of Information and Communication Technology. ICT encompasses the application of modern technology and devices such as mobile phones, internet, computer hardware and software. These devices can be used for dissemination of education and information, creating awareness on security, financial inclusion and management and health care facilities. This enables women to widen knowledge on world economy, develop association across the globe and enhanced global employment opportunities. ICT provides immense opportunities for the educational, economical, social development of women. With the empowerment of women through education, the use of ICT tools and devices for their communication purpose has enabled women to be successful in all sphere of life.

Women and SHGs

SHGs are the outcome of change in the view point of development program for women from welfare motive to more pragmatic, practical and result oriented. This was development by the Grameen Bank of Bangladesh founded by Mohammed Yunus in 1975. It is a group of women with similar economic background combine and join to form an association. Each member contribute fund and this fund is deposited and utilized as loan to the needy member of that group. A group consists of 12-20 women living below poverty line and residing in the same region. They select one animator and two representatives who are responsible for the functioning and maintaining of accounts of the group. In the year 2011, there were 23620 SHGs in Chennai city with 366110 women members and deposit of Rs. 9948.75 lakhs of savings (www.tamilnaduwomen.org). These are dominant for the development of women in the recent years particularly among the economically and socially backward communities. It provides employment and income to these women which have enhanced the social status of women. SHGs provide micro finance which is a powerful tool to eradicate poverty. This acts as a catalyst by promoting the habit of savings among women, provides loan when they need and also supports, helps, guides women to start up their own enterprise.

Review of Literature

Bimal Anjum & Rajesh Tiwari (2012) discussed the positive impact of ICT on women's empowerment and development. ICT has given a breakthrough to women's life style which was dominated by household works and child rearing and other traditional jobs. The accessibility to ICT has enriched women with knowledge and expertise which enable them to be hired in industrial sector especially in the IT sector which provide conducive work environment to women that lead to work-life balance. The use of ICT by the private sector has enhanced the accessibility of women to internet, smart cards; take up micro and small finance projects. This has led to increase in the number of women entrepreneurs who act as a catalyst and motivate other women who further leads to empowerment and development of women in India.

Hilaria Soundari (2016) explored the role of ICT in sustainable development and also traced the issues that stand in the way of development of women in rural areas. There were few areas that

required more ICT initiatives for rural development particularly women in rural areas. Education and training of technical skills and engendering of ICT policies were the tools which led to effective implementation of ICT in rural areas.

Lal B Suresh (2011) analyzed the various ICT tools such as e-learning, e-governance, e-finance, e-marketing, business process outsourcing and knowledge process outsourcing on empowering Indian women and also focussed the analysis on the changes required to be made in the educational sector. E-marketing had provided direct link between the women artisans and entrepreneurs and global market thereby eliminating middlemen and also provided all market information on global scenario and communication technology had provided broad based communication network for setting their products in the global market. E-education has eliminated the time and place constraint and helped women to continue their studies from their home at their convenient time.

Mini Amit Arrawatia & Pankaj Meel (2012) examined the significance of ICT in women's empowerment by studying the challenges and issues that hinder women from accessing ICT and also suggested measures to overcome the issues that led to women's empowerment. ICT had opened avenues for women in all the areas of social and political life and women had equal opportunities to access the benefits of these technology products and its services. ICT caters to the needs and provides information to women belonging to various strata of society. The information requirement of women was based on the level of education, place of living and their social conditions. The specific issues related to ICT were that the strategy adopted did not discuss the gender impairments, inaccessibility to ICT and linguistic problems. The study concluded that the policies and strategies undertaken to the implemented should be more based on gender development, prompt training on the benefits and usage of ICT and also program to create awareness among women particularly in rural areas will encompass and include more women in ICT premises that would lead to development of women.

Satya Nagamani & KrishnaVeni (2016) examined the ICT and women's empowerment and also studied the blockages of using ICT by women. Lack of policy pertaining to the use of ICT, poor infrastructure facilities, power cuts in rural areas, lack of training in computer hardware and software technologies, poor internet connections, language barrier as the content of ICT is only in English, lack of time cause majority of time gets wasted due to poor internet connections. Development of infrastructure facilities, training on language and computer maintenance would further enhance the number of women who access ICT.

Seied Beniamin & Manjunath (2016) assessed the impact of ICT on women's life in India. The study concluded that more men than women had access to and benefited from ICT. ICT played significant role in the development of weaker sections of a society particularly women. ICT enabled women in capacity building, better decision making which enhanced women's social and political participation.

Shradha Budhedeo (2016) addressed the challenges and issues hindering women in rural areas in the usage of ICT. Lack of time and fund, no trained instructors, traditional beliefs and attitude of rural people, problems in upgrading equipment, power fluctuations were the challenges faced by rural women in the implementation of ICT. To overcome these governments had taken many measures and initiatives such as projects on training of rural people in computer literacy, e-learning centres, IT curriculum, setup of telecentres to attend the ICT needs outside the classroom, etc. the study concluded that the co-operation of public and private would bridge the existing gap and also improvement in the accessibility and usage would lead to effective use of ICT in rural areas

Methodology

Scope of the Study

The study is intended to explore the impact of ICT on women empowerment and this will enable to know the significance of ICT and how ICT has changed the life of women and led to their development. The challenges faced by women while utilizing its services will create awareness on the areas women need to develop themselves.

Objectives of the Study

- To identify the challenges faced by women while using the ICT services.
- To study the awareness of ICT among women in SHGs.
- To list the empowerment attained by women in SHGs after using ICT.

Area of Study

The study area is limited to four sub-urban regions in Chennai city.

Source of data

The research uses both primary and secondary data. Primary data are collected through closed-ended structure questionnaires and secondary data are collected from various articles published in journals, newspapers, books and websites.

Limitations of the study

- The cost constraint limited the sample size to 20 SHGs in the sub-urban regions of Chennai.
- Due to limited time the study is conducted in sub-urban regions of Chennai which are developing areas.
- In few cases the women in SHGs faced language barrier and the researcher had to explain the questions in the regional language and get the responses.

Scope for Future Study

- Similar analysis can be undertaken on women in rural areas.
- Study can be conducted among women working in other sectors such as construction, domestic helpers.

Analysis of the Study

Challenges faced by women on SHGs while using ICT

The following are the challenges faced by women while utilizing the services of ICT. Illiteracy and lack of training pertain to person reasons because few of them were school drop outs and find it difficult to understand the applications and their benefits particularly e-banking facility which is very conducive for the payment and receiving of funds, e-marketing where inputs can be ordered online from the suppliers. Another serious problem faced by these women is accessing e-mail facility and had to depend on other member of the group. Other challenges are listed below:

- Illiteracy and lack of training
- Lack of affordability in downloading certain apps
- Lack of accessibility
- Content not in local language
- Insufficient funds
- Power cuts and shortages.
- Non availability of supplementary resources line scanner, printer, projector, multimedia etc.

Awareness about ICT among women in SHGs

The data collected indicated that majority of women in SHGs are aware of ICT tools and devices and are willing to access them for their personal and professional development. Women also show interest in learning about the device, application from other and utilize those services for their profession. Some women use for entertainment purpose also but majority of them used for official and professional reasons only. The common ICT tools applied are whatsapp, email, e-billing machines, use of computers for typing professional and official details and taking printout, scanners, etc.

Empowerment attained by women in SHGs after using ICT

Technical empowerment

- Developed technical and computing skills.
- Access to advanced technologies.
- Create knowledge about ICT.

Personal empowerment

- Enhanced self confidence.
- Understanding and speaking English required to communication purpose.
- Global information.
- Awareness about many laws and rules protecting women.
- Enables to know about women achievers.

Social empowerment

- Awareness about social issues.
- Participate in social media.
- Enters in group discussion.
- Social responsibility.
- New friends and supporters.

Economic empowerment

- Regular income.
- Improved standard of living.
- Better employment opportunities.
- Self employment
- Savings and investment.
- Purchase of assets.
- Repayment of debt.

Conclusion

This study shows that ICT plays a significant role in the empowerment of women in SHGs. In spite of the challenges listed, women find it easy to access ICT tools and devices. Development of ICT has positive impact on the empowerment of women by enhancing their awareness on gender equality, employment opportunities, self employment, enhanced knowledge and education.

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